

Fig. 5. Job's method of composition. Pd(II) Rubeanic acid α -picoline complex.
Pd(II) = Rubeanic acid = $1.175 \times 10^{-4} M$

Fig. 6. Molar ratio method of composition. Pd(II) Rubeanic acid α -picoline complex.
Pd(II) = Rubeanic acid = $1.7625 \times 10^{-4} M$

Fig. 7. Job's method of composition. Pd(II) Rubeanic acid collidine complex.
Pd(II) = Rubeanic acid = $1.175 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Fig. 8. Molar ratio method of composition. Pd(II) Rubeanic acid collidine complex.
Pd(II) = Rubeanic acid = $1.7625 \times 10^{-4} M$.

Effect of diverse ions: Solutions were prepared in the same way as described under absorbance curve with 2.5 ppm of palladium(II) in each case containing different amounts of each ionic species whose effects were studied. It is observed that copper(II), cobalt(II), nickel(II), platinum(IV), molybdenum(VI), vanadium(V), tungsten(VI), manganese(II) and chromium(III) interfered with the determination.

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Oxalylhydrazide: A New Reagent for Rapid Gravimetric Determination of Selenium

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THE growing importance of selenium in industry and chemistry is reflected by the large number of papers dealing with its determination by

different methods which have been nicely reviewed^{1,2}. The literature contains a number of methods based on the reduction of selenium(IV) and selenium(VI) to elemental selenium³⁻¹⁴. Based on the above principle the present paper describes the use of oxalyldihydrazide as a very convenient reagent for gravimetric determination of selenium. The method described allows rapid determination of selenium up to a minimum 5 mg. It has also been applied to selenium and tellurium mixtures for simultaneous estimation of both. Estimation of selenium can be done in the presence of several other foreign ions without the use of any masking agent.

Experimental

Apparatus : The elemental selenium was collected on a sintered glass crucible (porosity G 4). A single pan semi-micro balance, VEB Analytik SAHM-68, was used for weighing.

Reagents :

(a) **Selenium solution :** The selenium solution was prepared by dissolving reagent grade sodium selenite and the amount of selenium was gravimetrically determined by both sulphur dioxide^{1,2} and hydroxylamine^{1,2} methods. A working solution of 2 mg/ml Se was prepared by dilution

(b) **Oxalyldihydrazide solution :** A 2% w/v solution of oxalyldihydrazide was prepared in water. The reagent was prepared by reported method^{1,2}.

(c) Solution of foreign ions were prepared by the method of West¹⁵.

AnalaR grade HCl was used to maintain the acidity.

Procedure : A suitable aliquot of standard selenium solution was transferred to a beaker and diluted. 10 ml of 2% oxalyldihydrazide solution was added and the acidity maintained between 2-3 M with HCl to a final volume of 100 ml. The solution was boiled for 15 min for complete reduction and was filtered while warm on a sintered glass crucible. The precipitated selenium was washed with water and alcohol, dried at 110° and weighed. Results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1—RECOVERY OF SELENIUM

Sl. No.	Acidity=3 M HCl			
	Se taken mg	Se obtained* mg	Error %	Recovery %
1.	10	10.01	+0.10	100.10
2.	40	40.02	+0.05	100.05
3.	100	99.98	-0.02	99.98
4.	150	150.02	+0.01	100.01
5.	250	250.09	+0.04	100.04

*Mean of five replicates.

Determination of selenium and tellurium : Synthetic samples containing definite amounts of

selenium and tellurium were prepared. Selenium was determined by the recommended procedure. For the determination of tellurium, the filtrate was concentrated, 20 ml of 2% oxalyldihydrazide was added and the acidity was fixed to 6 M and above. The solution was boiled for 1 hr for complete reduction of tellurium. The precipitated tellurium was filtered on a sintered glass crucible, washed with water and alcohol, dried at 110° and weighed. Results are shown in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SELENIUM-TELLURIUM ANALYSIS IN SYNTHETIC SAMPLES

Acidity for Se=3 M HCl		Acidity for Te=6 M HCl		Se Recovery %	Te Recovery %
Se taken mg	Te taken mg	Se found* mg	Te found* mg		
20	10	19.97	10.02	99.80	100.20
20	20	19.98	19.99	99.90	99.95
20	40	20.01	40.01	100.05	100.03
40	60	39.99	60.01	99.97	100.01
40	100	39.98	99.98	99.95	99.98

*Mean of three replicates.

Results and Discussion

Preliminary experiments were conducted to find out the optimal conditions for complete reduction. The influence of the variables have been investigated.

Acidity : The optimal acidity range for complete reduction of selenium was found to be 2.5 to 8 M HCl. Effect of other acid media for reduction process was also studied. The reduction took more time in case of sulphuric acid and acetic acid whereas no reduction took place in case of nitric acid.

Amount of reagent : It was found out that 10 ml of 2% solution of oxalyldihydrazide was sufficient for the reduction of 250 mg of selenium.

Effect of foreign ions : Studies revealed that up to 20 fold excess of the following ions do not interfere : Cu(II), Ni(II), Mg(II), Mn(II), Zn(II), Hg(II), Cd(II), Co(II), Bi(III), Al(III), Sb(III), Fe(II), Fe(III), Sr(II), V(V), Nb(VI), Mo(VI), Ti(IV), Th(IV), Be(II), and up to 50 fold excess of NO₃⁻, PO₄³⁻, tartrate, citrate, EDTA, SO₄²⁻. In case of Ce(III), Cr(VI) and Fe(III), larger amount of reagent and longer heating time were required. Only tungsten interferes in the system but it can be first precipitated and then selenium can be determined in the filtrate.

Comparison with other methods : The proposed reagent is very suitable and selective for the determination of selenium. The reagent can be easily prepared, is stable and can be stored for long periods which is not possible with many of the reported methods^{3,11,12,14}. Another outstanding feature of this reagent is that it can be used for simultaneous estimation of selenium and tellurium.

The method is very fast as compared to other methods^{1, 6}.

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Detection and Determination of Phosphate Using Monomethyl-*p*-Amidophenol as Reagent

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MOST of the methods available for the detection and determination of phosphate are indirect involving complexation of phosphate with molybdenum(VI) and subsequent reduction of the phosphomolybdate. The reagents used for the detection of phosphate are ammonium molybdate and benzidine¹, *o*-dianisidine molybdate and hydrazine², quinolinium molybdate³ and ammonium molybdate and triphenyl methane dyes^{4, 5}. The reducing agents used for the development of the blue colour are tin(II) chloride⁶, hydroquinone⁷, hydrazine sulphate⁸, ascorbic acid⁹ and 1,2,4-aminonaphthol sulphonic acid¹⁰. A few other methods, involving extraction of the blue colour

into an immiscible organic layer are also reported. Very few reports are available for direct detection and determination of phosphate.

The method for detection and determination of phosphate reported in this communication, is a simple and direct one. The phosphate in solution, on reaction with monomethyl-*p*-amidophenol in 1-5 *N* HCl or in 1-10 *N* H₂SO₄, will oxidise it to purple-red *p*-N-methylquinone. The absorption spectrum of the purple-red coloured solution gives maximum absorption at 525 nm.

Materials and method :

Standard phosphate solution : 0.2197 g of potassium dihydrogen phosphate (previously dried at 110° for 1 hr and cooled in a desiccator) is dissolved in deionised water and diluted to 1 litre in a volumetric flask. 1 ml of this solution contains 0.05 mg P.

Monomethyl-*p*-amidophenol solution : 0.05 *M* solution is prepared by dissolving 17.190 g of the reagent (AnalaR grade) in 1 litre deionised water and standardised vanadometrically¹¹.

All other reagents used are of AnalaR grade unless otherwise mentioned.

Beckmann-26 spectrophotometer with auto recorder is used for spectral measurements.

Experimental

Detection of phosphate in a test tube : 0.5 ml of the test solution is taken in a test tube and 0.5 ml of monomethyl-*p*-amidophenol reagent solution is added followed by 1.5 ml of 2.5 *N* HCl. A purple-red colour develops immediately on shaking the test tube which indicates the presence of phosphate.

Limit of detection—2.63 µg/2.5 ml

Limit of dilution—1 : 2,000

Detection of phosphate on a spot plate : 0.04 ml of the test solution is taken in the cavity of the spot plate. 0.04 ml of the reagent followed by 0.04 ml HCl (1 : 4) are added and mixed with a glass rod. An immediate purple-red colour, stable for 48 hr indicates the presence of orthophosphate.

Limit of detection—0.53 µg/0.12 ml

Limit of dilution—1 10,000

Photometric determination of phosphate : To a known volume of the sample solution containing 4-13 µg of P in a 10 ml volumetric flask are added successively 3 ml of 0.05 *M* monomethyl-*p*-amidophenol and 1 ml of conc. HCl. The volume is made up to the mark with distilled water. The absorbance of the purple-red coloured solution, the oxidation product of the reagent, is measured at 525 nm against a reagent blank.

Typical results are presented in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

By preliminary experiments it is found that the acidity should be in between 1-5 *N* for HCl and